

ES076 and ES077 were tolerant of 12 °C water at the seedling stage (see table). Afaa Kilombero 1-196 was highly tolerant and Afaa Mwanza 1-104, Supa India, ES013, ES040, ES043, ES059, ES060, ES072, ES078, and ES081 tolerant of 17 °C night air temperature for 5 d during panicle initiation.

Gamti, Afaa Mwanza 0-746, Lindi Safari, ES003, ES018, ES042, ES044, ES053, ES054, ES082, and HR19 were tolerant of 21 °C air temperature for 5 d during anthesis.

ES076 showed tolerance at both seedling stage and heading. Afaa

Kilombero 1-196, Supa India, ES040, ES059, and ES072 were tolerant at panicle initiation and heading.

Afaa lines, Supa India, and Kihogo, the varieties commonly grown, are tolerant at panicle initiation, but susceptible at anthesis. □

Response of rice varieties to planting time during the dry season

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In parts of Orissa, rice is grown early in the dry season (DS) using water from streams, tanks, and ponds that dry up in Apr and May. We studied varietal response to different planting times during Dec and Jan. The trials were laid out in a replicated split-plot design in DS 1985 and 1986. Varieties Pathara, Kuber, and Rajani were studied in 1985; Pathara, Rajani, Annapurna, and Shankar in 1986.

Soil was laterite, loamy sand, with pH 5.6, 0.4% organic carbon, 0.04% total N, 12 kg available P, and 150 kg available K/ha. Seedlings were transplanted at 25 d at 15- × 10-cm spacing with 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha. Full P and K and 25% N were applied basal, 50% N at tillering, and 25% N at panicle initiation. Four

Temperature profile during the rice-growing season. Bhubaneswar, India, 1985-86.

transplanting dates, at 154 intervals, started 5 Dec 1985 and 10 Dec 1986.

Time of planting affected yield (see table). Transplantings on 25 Dec 1985

and 5 Jan 1987 produced the highest. Late and early planting reduced yield, perhaps because of temperature (see figure). □

Effect of date of transplanting on yield of different rice varieties. Bhubaneswar, Orissa, India, 1985-86.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)	
	1985	1986
<i>Planting date</i>		
5-10 Dec	2.8	2.0
20-25 Dec	3.1	2.6
5-10 Jan	3.7	2.4
20-25 Jan	3.3	2.2
LSD (0.05)	0.5	0.1
<i>Variety</i>		
Pathara (OR83-23)	3.1	2.3
Kuber (OR164-5)	3.1	-
Rajani (OR163-104)	3.5	2.4
Annapurna	-	2.6
Shankar	-	1.9
LSD (0.05)	0.3	0.1

Inheritance of seedling stage cold tolerance in 6 indica and japonica crosses

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We used highly cold-tolerant japonica varieties Zhonghua 8 and Reimei as the female parents (P_1) and cold-susceptible indica varieties Ejiufeng, My 821 66, Qinghuaai 6, and Conggui 314 as the male parents (P_2) to make six crosses (two including B_2 , F_1/P_2) between indicas and japonicas in 1985-86.

The seeds were sown in 50- × 20- ×

15-cm plastic trays, one cross (including P_1 , P_2 , F_1 , F_2 , B_2)/tray. Seedlings at the 3-leaf stage were subjected to 10/6 °C day/night, 12 h light (2500-3500 lx)/d for 7 d in the incubator. We used leaf rolling as the criterion for cold tolerance.

All F_1 s showed good tolerance for low temperature. The F_2 and B_2 populations had only R or S seedlings. Segregation of F_2 plants in 6 crosses fit a 15:1 inheritance ratio, B_2 plants in 2 crosses fit 3:1 (see table). That shows that cold tolerance indicated by leaf rolling in indicas and japonicas is governed by two dominant duplicate genes. □